

1. Effect of sesbania green manure and wheat straw on ammonia volatilization in flooded Ludhiana soil, India.

2. Effect of sesbania green manure and wheat straw on floodwater NH₄⁺-N concentration. Ludhiana, India.

maintain 5 cm standing water. Floodwater temperatures ranged from 28.5 to 33 °C. Two pots/treatment were fitted with chambers continuously flushed with NH₃-free compressed air.

Soil test fertilizer recommendations increase economic yields of rice

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We compared bases for N application recommendations—state, soil test, and farmers' practice in a farmer's field during 1986.

Soil of the experimental field was sandy loam (Typic Ustochrept) with pH (1:2) 8.4, 0.36% organic C, EC (1:2) 0.10 dS/m, CEC 10.9 meq/100 g soil, 190 kg available N/ha (alkaline permanganate method), 8.0 kg available P/ha (NaHCO₃ extract), and 305 kg available K (ammonium acetate extract)/ha. Available Zn was 0.5 ppm (DTPA

NH₃ that evolved from incubated samples was collected at intervals using a manifold, and estimated by absorbing in 2% boric acid-mixed indicator solution. Floodwater samples also were taken to analyze NH₄⁺-N.

Rate of N loss by ammonia volatilization in flooded soil was markedly affected by type of amendment (Fig. 1). Incorporating wheat straw resulted in the greatest N loss due to volatilization. At 16 d, cumulative ammonia volatilization was 11% for wheat straw + N, 4.5% for N alone, and 1% for green manure + N.

No ammonia volatilization occurred in the soil amended with green manure alone. In the soil amended with wheat straw, NH₃ volatilization could already be detected at 2 d, the first sampling.

Ammoniacal N concentration in the floodwater was greatest in soil amended with wheat straw + N (Fig. 2).

These results suggest that higher N losses through ammonia volatilization in straw-amended soil were probably due to the high rate of urea application. Incorporation of wheat straw may have changed the urease kinetic parameters, which seem dependent on the organic material incorporated. □

extractable). Nutrient limits used for recommendations were as follows:

	Nutrient limits (kg/ha) (elemental form)			
	N	P	K	Zn(ppm)
Low	<250	<5	<125	<0.6
Medium	250-500	5-10	125-300	
High	>500	>10	>300	

Seedlings of PR106 (30-35 d) duration were transplanted. Each treatment received the following nutrients:

	Nutrients (kg/ha) (elemental form)			
	N	P	K	ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O
State recommendation	125	26.20	50	25
Soil test recommendation	125	17.47	-	-
Farmers' practice	125	-	-	-

One-third N and all the P, K, Zn were applied at transplanting. The remaining N was applied in 2 equal splits at 3 and

Effect of basis for fertilizer application rate on yield, yield attributes, and profit in rice.^a

	State recommendation schedule	Soil test recommendation	Farmers' practice	LSD at 5%
Rough rice yield (t/ha)	6.7	7.2	5.0	0.2
Increase in yield (t/ha) over farmers' practice	1.7	2.2	–	
Expenditure on fertilizers (\$/ha)	96.25	67.90	47.50	
Increase in fertilizer expenditure over farmers' practice (\$/ha)	48.75	20.40	–	
Yield price (\$/ha)	939.40	1008.00	701.40	
Net profit (\$/ha)	550.20	647.15	360.95	
Increase in profit over farmers' practice (\$/ha)	189.25	286.20	–	
Increase in profit over state fertilizer schedule (\$/ha)	–	96.95	–	
Yield attributes				
Plant ht (cm)	111.0	107.7	105.9	3.8
1000-grain wt (g)	20.7	21.8	19.2	ns
Number of tillers	8.1	8.4	6.9	0.9

^aPrice (\$/kg); N, 0.38; P, 0.51; K, 0.19; Zn, 0.27; paddy, 0.14. Expenditure on all agricultural operations (\$/ha) = 292.95.

6 wk after transplanting. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

Soil test fertilizer recommendation resulted in significantly higher economic yields (see table). State fertilizer schedule resulted in significantly higher yields over farmers' practice. □

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Source and time of phosphate application in irrigated rice

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We studied the effect of basal and split application of phosphate through single superphosphate (6.9% P), diammonium phosphate (18-20.0), and ammonium polyphosphate (12-25.2-0) on irrigated rice in 1987 wet season, in a randomized block design with 4 replications.

Soil was sandy loam with pH 6.2, 0.47% organic C, CEC 5.2 meq/ 100 g soil, 9 kg Olsen's P/ ha, 0.15 meq exchangeable K/ 100 g soil, and 1.5 ppm available Zn (DTPA extractable). Daya (125 d) was transplanted 27 Jul with 80-33.3 kg NK/ha. Diammonium phosphate and ammonium polyphosphate at 80 kg N/ha were applied in 50-25-25 splits. Phosphate was mixed with double the weight of soil, wet to less than field capacity, and broadcast over 5 cm water in the field.

Significantly higher yields were obtained with 26 kg P/ ha, irrespective of source and time of application (see table). Highest yield (4.82 t/ ha) was with split application of ammonium

Effect of source and time of phosphate application on yield and yield response, Bhubaneswar, India, 1987.

Source ^a	Rate (kg P/ha) and time of application		Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Panicle wt (g)	Yield response (kg grain/kg p)
	Basal	Tillering (21 d)				
Control	0	0	2.7	170	1.33	–
DAP	13	0	3.0	213	1.61	22.3
DAP	26	0	3.6	270	1.86	37.3
DAP	6.5	6.5	3.2	228	1.67	41.5
DAP	13	13	3.9	282	1.85	48.4
SSP	13	0	3.2	222	1.54	41.5
SSP	26	0	3.7	275	1.65	39.6
SSP	6.5	6.5	3.1	226	1.61	33.8
SSP	13	13	3.7	268	1.80	37.7
APP	13	0	3.6	251	2.01	53.8
APP	26	0	4.3	303	2.02	63.4
APP	6.5	6.5	3.8	277	2.03	84.6
APP	13	13	4.8	308	2.19	82.3
LSD (0.05)			0.4	24	0.15	–

^aDAP = diammonium phosphate, SSP = single superphosphate, APP = ammonium polyphosphate.

polyphosphate at 26 kg P/ha. Grain yields in general were low because of continuous rain, coupled with strong wind at flowering.

Panicle number/m² and panicle weight were highest on split application of 26 kg P/ha as ammonium polyphosphate. □

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